

THE POLICY OF THE SOVIET GOVERNMENT REGARDING THE ISLAMIC RELIGION AND WAQF PROPERTIES IN UZBEKISTAN (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE 20S OF THE XX CENTURY)

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Annotation: This article, based on information available in the scientific literature, materials and periodicals, highlights questions about the religious policies of the Soviet government in Uzbekistan in the 20s of the 20th century.

Key words: Soviet government, Uzbekistan, charitable property, economic base, madrasah, expropriation, state discretion.

From the point of view of Islamic religious teachings, waqfs are considered charitable properties, and they were established mainly for charitable purposes. They also served as the economic basis of madrasahs. It should be noted that in the second half of the 20s of the 20th century, madrasahs operated in a certain way. After the establishment of Soviet power in Turkestan, the Bolsheviks tried to forcibly transfer the endowments to the state, that is, to expropriate them.

The transfer of Waqf properties to the state began after the October coup of 1917. This issue was based on the decree "On Land"[1;13] adopted by the Second All-Russian Diet of the Soviets on October 26, 1917, because according to it, all lands, including lands of churches and religious institutions, are "public property". It was announced that private ownership of land was abolished.

In 1918, the People's Commissariat of Nations was established in Turkestan, and in December, a department for management of endowment properties was established in the People's Commissariat of Nations [2;8]. The employees of the People's Commissariat of Nations have been in favor of turning foundations into state property since the first days of their activity. According to the leaders of the commissariat, the laws of the Soviet government, including the decree on land, abolished the private ownership of the means of production and land, therefore, the endowment lands and other properties should be turned into state property[3;5]. According to the decision of the Central Executive Committee of the Republic of Turkestan on February 26, 1920, endowments were placed at the disposal of the People's Commissariat of Education [4; 2].

At the meeting of the People's Commissariat of Education of the Turkestan ASSR on March 6, 1920, the issue of creating a foundation department was considered. By its decision, the collegium established a foundation department, the task of director was temporarily assigned to Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, and he was entrusted with the task of finding a candidate for the directorship of the foundation department [5;118]. According to Munavvar Qori's recommendation, B. Khojayev was appointed as the head of the foundation department under the People's Commissariat of Education. Soon, the People's Commissariat of Education developed the "Temporary Regulation on Endowment Management" [5; 128, 132]. According to the regulation, the Central Waqf Department was established under the People's

Commissariat of Education for the administration of waqfs. Madrasas, mosques and other religious organizations are entrusted with the direct management of waqf properties together with a two-person collegium.

In the decision of the Central Executive Committee of Turkestan on February 26, 1920, no specific instructions were given on the purpose of using the income of the foundation properties. In the subsequent decisions of the government of Turkestan related to endowments, this issue was clarified to a lesser extent. On April 14, 1920, in the theses of the Turkestan regional committee of the Bureau of the Republican Communist Party (b) on the land issue: "Waqf properties are given to the people's commissariat of land affairs. The income from these lands will be given to the educational commissariat and used for cultural and educational activities among the Muslim population" [6; 108], it was said.

Pursuant to the Regulation of the CEC of the Republic of Turkestan dated November 17, 1920 "On land use and land structure in the Republic of Turkestan", all land and water in the territory of Turkestan, regardless of who uses it, became the property of the state and the people. For example, "All foundation lands will be transferred to the People's Commissariat of Education for the establishment of kindergartens, orphanages, commune-schools, and other cultural-educational organizations, and those not used for these purposes will be given to land development works in general order"[7;38] was shown. In this regulation of the government, it was noted that the waqf lands are state property, and the right to use them was given to the People's Commissariat of Education. In this way, from November 1920, the waqf lands, which formed the economic basis of madrasas in Turkestan, were transferred to the state [8; 17]. This caused a feeling of discontent among the local Muslim population.

The growing armed resistance movement in Central Asia has also worried the government and party authorities. On May 18, 1922, the Central Committee of the Bureau of the Republican Communist Party (b) passed a decision "On Turkestan-Bukhara Affairs" and instructed the local soviet and party bodies that it was necessary to "return the Waqf lands to their former owners." The Central Executive Committee of Turkestan discussed this important way-guidelines on the foundation of the center at its Plenum on May 26, 1922 [9; 952].

On June 20, 1922, the Turkestan CEC decree No. 75 "On returning endowments to madrasas and mosques of the Republic of Turkestan" was issued [10; 145,149]. According to him, the endowments were returned to their previous owners.

On October 29, 1922, a meeting of the Turkestan Communist Party CEC with representatives of the People's Commissariats of Internal Affairs, Land and Water Affairs and Justice was held. A commission consisting of U.Eshonhojayev, I.Khidiraliev, A.Solovyev and a representative of the People's Commissariat of Justice was formed [11;18]. determined the terms of doing it and later transfer to the discretion of the state[12; 297].

On December 28, 1922, a new decree of Turkestan CEC No. 173 "On Endowments" was signed. According to it, Decree No. 75 of June 20, 1922 was canceled. According to this decree, waqf properties were divided according to the direction of the relevant office, that is, from waqfs related to madrasahs, schools, orphanages, cemeteries, which have a religious status and are spent on cultural-educational and patronage. allowed to use. On January 11, 1923, in accordance with Decree No. 173, the General Foundation Department and its departments were established under the People's Commissariat of Education of the Turkestan ASSR [13;2]. The board consisted of organizational and informational, academic (scientific institution),

financial and economic departments. The staff of the General Waqf Department was set to consist of 14 people, and the Waqf departments consisted of 12 people. The main task of the General Foundation Department was to account for foundation properties, check the original documents of foundations, as well as to rebuild madrasas in the Soviet style, and to supervise cultural and educational work in them [14; 81].

Based on the above, appropriate measures have been determined by the General Foundation Department. A program for the reconstruction of madrasahs and the organization of cultural and educational activities in them was developed and implemented. According to the appendix in paragraph 14 of Decree No. 173, madrasahs that did not use the new programs were deprived of the right to use the income of the foundation.

The procedure for using the income from endowments of madrasahs and other religious institutions was a constant focus of the Soviet authorities. An example of this is the expanded meeting of the Central Committee of the Republic of Turkestan on March 17, 1923. The issue of foundation funds was discussed at this meeting. The SSC decided that it is necessary to recognize only foundations of cultural and educational importance. These funds were primarily allocated for the provision of Soviet schools, only a part of which was allocated for madrasahs [14; 89]. It can be seen from this that since 1923, the Soviet government began to limit the economic base of madrasahs in order to end their activities. The main foundation administration was responsible for the direct implementation of this policy of the Soviet government and their sovietization.

On June 19-20, 1923, the 11th Congress of Soviets of the Turkestan ASSR was held. It discussed the implementation of the decisions of the Council of People's Commissars and regional executive committees. The role of the General Foundation Department was important in the implementation of this work. The issue of national education was considered in the decision of the 11th Diet of Soviets. In the decision of the Syezd: "The issue of endowment should be solved by using the income of endowment properties, first of all, by using the Soviet and new method schools as much as possible from the lower stages, and in order to fight against the priests, to give ample opportunity to use national intellectuals in new method madrasahs, schools, and educational work." [14; 81], it was noted.

In September 1923, the reformed madrasahs, which were transformed into a new method, were entrusted with the direct management of educational work. Cultural and educational institutions - madrasa mutallila are appointed by the waqf department [14; 157].

In the report of the People's Commissariat of Education on December 6, 1923, it was said: "The General Foundation Department allocated 65 percent of the funds for the Sovietization of madrasahs and their maintenance, as well as the construction of the first-stage nine-year school buildings and cultural and educational institutions. 20 percent and 15 percent were spent on household needs" [14; 89]. In 1923, 10,000 deciles of waqf land, which were transferred to most waqf departments of the General Waqf Administration, were distributed to poor farmers in early 1924 [14; 82].

Since the mid-20s of the 20th century, the control of the Soviet government over madrasahs has become particularly strong. In many cities and districts of the republic, cases of interference in the internal affairs of madrasahs and their forced closure have been observed. For example, the students of the Kesak Kurgan madrasa located in the Old City of Tashkent were forcibly expelled by Soviet law enforcement officers and their cells were

sealed. The head of the madrasa was arrested on the same day [15; 43]. In 1923-1924, 10 madrasas operating in the city of Tashkent were forcibly closed [16; 37].

From January 1, 1924, 212 madrasahs in Turkestan were registered by the General Foundation Department, and their gradual closure began. Their buildings were adapted to the new Soviet schools and began to be rebuilt [13; 54]. Religious subjects were completely removed from the curricula of madrasahs.

In early 1925, the General Waqf Administration of Uzbekistan wrote a report to one of the leading agencies about the state of endowments in the former Republic of Turkestan. nearby schools were reformed. The rest, as well as the almshouses, were either closed or removed from the endowment's income. The reason for their closure was that the buildings and rooms of many madrassas, schools, and religious institutions were completely unsuitable for current schools, their reconstruction required a lot of money, and the number of students in madrassas was not so large. From April 1, 1924, the reformed madrassas were transferred to the II stage of the single - labor (Soviet) school of the People's Commissariat of Education. Religious Muslim schools in Tashkent, Fergana and Samarkand regions - madrassas, schools, orphanages are currently not provided with funds from the foundation" [17; 652].

In accordance with the decision of the CEC of the Soviet Union on January 18, 1925 and the decision "On the reform of old-style schools, madrasas and orphanages" issued by the Tashkent Old City Executive Committee in December of the same year, the Soviet foundation agencies aggressively The funds received from the properties of the religious foundation, as well as from the properties of madrasahs and other religious organizations, were mainly used to provide Soviet schools and other educational institutions. In 1925, 113 Soviet schools with 4,946 students were supported by the endowment [18; 147].

In 1925-1926, in the process of land and water reform in Fergana, Tashkent and Samarkand regions, cultural and educational endowment lands were transferred to the state land fund, along with the rich and state lands, and were distributed to poor farmers. Preparations for this reform were started based on the decision of the 1st Diet of Soviets of Uzbekistan held in February 1925. The government of Uzbekistan has set the following tasks: "The work of land calculation in the former Turkestan, the territory of Uzbekistan, should be strengthened and completed by the beginning of the new economic year. In this period and in this area, the identification of state and foundation lands (those not leased for a long period) should be finished, and from the autumn of 1925, the work of giving land to farmers with little land and landless should be started" [19; 86].

On December 2, 1925, the Central Executive Committee of the USSR adopted the decree "On Land and Water Reform" [20; 15,18]. On the basis of this decree, all the lands of landlords with more than 40 tens of irrigated land in Fergana region and more than 50 tens of irrigated land in Tashkent and Samarkand regions, as well as the land of large merchants who use their land by hiring labor, and the land of businessmen living in the city done.

In Uzbekistan, the issue of liquidation of endowment properties of madrasas was raised for the second time when a new draft of the decree "On endowments" was submitted to the approval of the Central Committee of the Ministry of Education and Culture, and later on December 19, 1925, the Ministry of Education of the USSR adopted a decision "On endowments". when it was done, it was put quite strictly.

On December 19, 1925, CEC he Uzbek SSR adopted Resolution No. 168 "On Foundations"[21;1]. According to this decision, the property of foundations established for

cultural, educational and socially beneficial purposes is considered state property. With this, he was deprived of endowments, which are the economic basis of madrasahs.

On August 15, 1927, the Ministry of Education and Culture of Uzbekistan adopted a decision "On the transfer of the foundation properties to the care of the People's Commissariat of Education of the Uzbek SSR." In the decision, it was noted that all properties should be recognized as cultural and educational endowment properties, and they should be placed under the care and discretion of the People's Commissariat of Education of the USSR [22; 19].

By order of the People's Commissariat of Education of the Ukrainian SSR, according to the decision of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Ukrainian SSR dated August 15, and the decision of the journal of the Ukrainian SSR Central Committee dated October 1, 1927, the General Foundation Department and its local departments were abolished from October 1, 1927 [23; 203].

This legal document made significant changes to the decision of the CEC of Uzbekistan "On Endowments" approved on December 19, 1925. With this decision, the authorities of the republic declared religious foundations as state property. According to the decision of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications of Ukraine No. 99 of August 15, 1927, all foundation properties, both cultural and educational and religious foundation properties, were leased to local economic departments until October 1, 1927. Maarif was transferred to the care of the People's Commissariat [24;29].

On September 27, 1927, the Central Committee of the Ukrainian SSR decided to transfer the foundation properties from the General Foundation Administration to local economic agencies. According to it [25; 60]: - The People's Commissariat of Education hands over endowments to the local economic administration (Mestkhoz) for use. Trade, industry, warehouse buildings, abjuvoz, mills, baths, brick factories, gardens, residential and farm facilities, teahouses, madrassas, and the lands serving the religious houses under the jurisdiction of the People's Commissariat of Education will be handed over to the Department of Agriculture.

According to the decision of the CEC of the Soviets of the Uzbek SSR and the Council of People's Commissars of September 22, 1928 "On the transfer of foundation properties to the property of local Soviets", the cultural, educational and religious foundations under the jurisdiction of the People's Commissariat of Education are considered the property of local Soviets. published [26;48].

Based on this decision, amendments were made to the decision of the Soviets of the Central Committee of the Ukrainian SSR No. 99 of August 15, 1927 "On the transfer of foundation properties to the care of the People's Commissariat of Education of the Ukrainian SSR". According to the decision, the cultural-educational and religious endowment properties under the care of the People's Commissariat of Education were considered the property of the local Soviets [27; 15]. This decision came into full force on October 1, 1928. According to the decision, the endowment properties of all religious institutions were liquidated, they were turned into the property of local Soviets. The Central Committee of the SSR and the Central Committee of the Soviet Union allow the local soviets to give the buildings of the mosques for prayer in accordance with the prescribed procedure, with the recommendation of the religious communities. With this, the madrasahs were deprived not only of their waqf properties, but also of their buildings. The last land and water reform in Uzbekistan was

implemented in Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya and Khorezm districts in 1928-1929. On November 1, 1928, the Central Executive Committee of Uzbekistan adopted the resolution "On ending land use without large-scale labor in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya districts of the Uzbek SSR" and on December 2, 1928 "On ending land use without large-scale labor in Khorezm district" on" decrees. As shown above, based on the decision of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications of Uzbekistan dated August 15, 1927, religious foundation lands were also declared state property. Based on this, it was written in both decisions: "The following lands shall be transferred to the land provision fund for landless and landless peasants... former cultural, educational and religious endowments" [28].

The 4th session of the CEC of Soviets of the II convocation of Uzbekistan will be held on November 13-19, 1928. Waqf issues were also discussed there. According to it, the government makes a special decision on the transfer of former cultural-educational, religious endowment lands within the state land property to landless and landless peasants and labor unions for use [29; 262]. Based on the decision, the waqf lands of all madrasas were distributed to poor, poor, landless and poor farmers. This strict decision issued by the government led to the complete disappearance of the waqf properties of madrasahs. On November 18, 1928, the IV session of the second convocation of the Soviets of the CEC of the USSR adopted a decision "On the termination of old-style schools and madrasas" [30; 15.61]. Clause 3 of this decision is related to the termination of madrasahs as well as other religious schools, i.e. it is incumbent on the district executive committees to strictly implement the existing laws and orders on religious schools, including madrasahs, religious schools [31]. Based on the above decision, all madrassas in the Uz SSR were closed. With this, the sole rule of the Soviet education system came into full force [32; 26].

In conclusion, it should be noted that from the beginning of the 20s of the 20th century, madrassas, which are places of religious higher education, were reformed in the Turkestan ASSR, but the reform process did not last long. In 1924, madrasahs were transferred to the program of the second stage of the single labor school at the initiative of the General Foundation Department and were Sovietized. They also operated until 1928, despite various restrictions. The Soviet authorities tried to forcibly transfer the foundation properties, which are the economic base of the madrasas, to the state. In 1928, according to the decision of the Soviets of the USSR CEC and Council of People's Commissars, the madrasa endowment properties were turned into the property of the local Soviets. Madrasahs were closed and their buildings were handed over to various organizations and institutions. Thus, madrasahs with a thousand-year history were stopped and their waqf lands were distributed to poor farmers. This, without a doubt, had a negative impact on the formation of the enlightenment and spiritual image of the indigenous population.

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